

1 **Amelioration of pulmonary immune activation to support ventilation through alveolar regeneration:**
2 **CCL5.**

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7 Chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (COPD) include the condition emphysema wherein the alveoli in
8 the lung which contract and expand to conduct gas exchange are damaged and the sufferer experiences
9 limited ventilation (breathing) (1-3). Tissue damage and pathology resulting from immune activation is a
10 theme in pulmonary biology (4-6). We measured total transcription in the lungs of humans with COPD
11 and in healthy control individuals to identify immune activation-associated factors that contribute to
12 disease pathology and tissue damage in emphysema (7). We identified the C-C motif chemokine ligand
13 *CCL5* among the gene products whose expression was most significantly up-regulated and differentially
14 expressed transcriptome-wide in the lungs of humans with COPD. *CCL5* was transcriptionally
15 co-regulated with the T-lymphocyte marker *CD8a*, the cytotoxic T-lymphocyte effectors granzyme *GZMA*
16 and *GZMH*, and the inflammasome-associated genes guanylate binding proteins *GBP4* and *GBP5* in the
17 human lung. Targeting and neutralization of *CCL5* is a viable therapeutic strategy to limit immune
18 pathology and support enhanced ventilation through regeneration of the alveoli in humans with a leading
19 cause of mortality, emphysema.
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We studied whole transcription in the human lung, in health and in humans with the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease emphysema, to understand the molecular mechanisms underlying tissue damage and pathology in COPD.

Figure 1: CCL5 is produced in large quantities in the lungs of patients with emphysema.

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$n=19$ lung tissue from $n=6$ individuals (control)

$n=37$ lung tissue from $n=11$ humans with COPD (emphysema)

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	% DE
6352	1.90e-31	0.191	-11.666067	-2.2280959	311.65	CCL5	5/15183	99.97

Next, we utilized a next-generation systems biological method (8) to understand the function of CCL5 in the lung by querying multiple tissue settings to identify its transcriptionally co-regulated gene partners.

Figure 2: Expression of CCL5 in the lung is associated with transcription of CD8A, GBP4 and GBP5, and GZMA and GZMH.

1 In the human lung, CCL5 was transcriptionally co-regulated with the inflammasome-associated
2 genes GBP4 and GBP5, the cytotoxic T-lymphocyte granzymes GZMA and GZMH as well as the
3 T-lymphocyte marker CD8A.

4 **Discussion**

5 We identified here CCL5 as a central component of the gene signature of human emphysema, a
6 leading cause of death in humans.

7 **References**

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